

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Nogas, E. M., Póvoa, A. C. S., & Pech, W. (2023). Decision-making under stress: The hiding behind a small cake effect. Revista de Administração Contemporânea, 27(6), e230023. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2023230023.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Nogas, E. M., Póvoa, A. C. S., Pech, W., & Kiseleva, M. (2023). Peer review report for: Decision-making under stress: The hiding behind a small cake effect. RAC. Revista de Administração Contemporânea. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10278316>

REVIEWERS:

- Meg Kiseleva (Cardiff University, United Kingdom)
The other reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Meg Kiseleva
Date review returned: March 28, 2023
Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

An interesting study into the links between induced stress, measured through salivary cortisol levels, and behaviour in the ultimatum game with asymmetric information. The authors found that participants in the stress condition made more generous offers and were more confident that the responders guessed the true endowment correctly.

One of the main strength of this paper is a randomised experiment comparing responses in stress and no-stress conditions. I recommend this paper for acceptance with minor revisions, indicated in the comments below.

Introduction

Since you draw from the literature that found that stress is associated with poorer decision making and application of analytical skills, it would be helpful to understand whether you view deception as something that requires analytical thinking.

This introductory section would benefit from a more neatly constructed argument drawing from what prior literature says about possible mechanisms for the links between stress and decision making and what that means for the possibility of opportunistic behaviour.

A brief introduction to System 1 and System 2 (or Type 1 and Type 2 processes, as they are increasingly referred to since there is no evidence for distinct systems in the human brain responsible for the different kinds of thinking) before using the terms is warranted.

It would be helpful to make sure that all descriptions of the methods used in this study are in the Method section and everything related to the results is in Results or Conclusion rather than in the introduction.

Methods

What random assignment procedure was used?

The readability of this section would benefit from placing all background information about the measurement of salivary cortisol and about the stress induction into separate respective sub-sections so that Procedures can focus on a step-by-step account of what the participants did.

Since all (100%) of the proposers received R\$30, it needs to be made clear that the probability distribution communicated to the responders (R\$10 with 50% probability, R\$20 with 25% probability, and R\$30 with 25% probability) was not the true distribution.

Table 1 needs the standard deviations in addition to the means.

What were the criteria for selecting participants?

Results

What are the standard deviations for the offers (Table 3)?

Could you elaborate on 'the costs of deceiving the responder'? (p15, para 1)

It would also be interesting to see a bar chart showing a distribution of offers by reported beliefs about the responder's guess in the two groups (a combination of Figures 2 and 3).

Regarding the regression models, it is very interesting to see the relationships between stress and offers. However, your Belief variable is an interaction between stress treatment and the belief the responders guessed the true endowment correctly. While you do have Stress in Models 3 to 5, the main effect of the belief the responders guessed the true endowment correctly is missing from all the models where Beliefs is used and Stress is missing from Model 2. I suggest adding both the main effects and the interaction term.

For your cortisol variable, it would make sense to use cortisol levels at Time 2, rather than the difference between Time 1 and Time 2, as your independent variable. That would account for the actual stress rather than for the effectiveness of the stress treatment.

Finally, a rationale for using the Tobit regression is warranted. Do you expect the true values to extend beyond the observed data? If so, why?

Conclusions

The claim that most of the literature on decision making and stress shows that stressed individuals usually search for a reward that benefits them can be easily contested.

How are your findings situated within the existing literature? E.g., there has been a lot of research on negative affect and risk perception, and on risk perception and risk taking.

A couple of other things to consider:

Do you expect the participants' majors (economics, business administration, or accounting) to have any influence on the way they approached the task? Economics majors may be familiar with the ultimatum game.

Since some of the participants (only in the stress condition) offered 0 or 30, both of which would result in them getting 0, is it likely that they misunderstood or forgot the instructions (potentially because of the stress)?

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: No

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).: None

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 3. Average

Originality: 3. Average

Overall: 3. Average

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Responses

Dear Reviewers and Editor,

We are grateful to both reviewers and the editor for the opportunity to revise our paper. Your comments provide us with the occasion to rethink and organize your paper. We tried to incorporate most of the observations requested. Thank you again.

Comments:

Reviewer 1:

Reviewer 1: Since you draw from the literature that found that stress is associated with poorer decision-making and application of analytical skills, it would be helpful to understand whether you view deception as something that requires analytical thinking.

Our answer: In this paper, we tried to understand the potential relation between stress and deceptive behavior since, according to the literature, stressful decisions can favor deception. On the other hand, stress can also decrease the potential for deception when the decision requires analytical thinking. So, the central aspect of our research was the role of stress and its relation to deception. The limits of our study do not allow us to be focused on deception itself but on the deceptive behavior of people when under stress.

Reviewer 1: This introductory section would benefit from a more neatly constructed argument drawing from what prior literature says about possible mechanisms for the links between stress and decision-making and what that means for the possi-

bility of opportunistic behavior.

Our answer: We changed our introduction to address this observation.

Reviewer 1: A brief introduction to System 1 and System 2 (or Type 1 and Type 2 processes, as they are increasingly referred to since there is no evidence for distinct systems in the human brain responsible for the different kinds of thinking) before using the terms is warranted.

Our answer: Done! We also changed the word "system" to "type". We inserted a more comprehensive explanation regarding the dual process theory in the footnote since the basis of this theory, even a brief one, became the introduction too long and confusing.

Reviewer 1: It would be helpful to ensure that all descriptions of the methods used in this study are in the Method section and everything related to the results is in Results or Conclusion rather than in the introduction.

Our answer: We have modified the introduction text to ensure that the Method and Results descriptions are in their appropriate sessions.

Reviewer 1: What random assignment procedure was used?

Our answer: We used two labs: A and B. Upon arriving at the experiment, each participant was randomly conducted to lab A or B. We explained this aspect in more detail in the new version of the paper.

Reviewer 1: The readability of this section would benefit from placing all background information about the measurement of salivary cortisol and stress induction into separate sub-sections so that Procedures can focus on a step-by-step account of what the participants did.

Our answer: Done!

Reviewer 1: Since all (100%) of the proposers received R\$30; it needs to be made clear that the probability distribution communicated to the responders (R\$10 with 50% probability, R\$20 with 25% probability, and R\$30 with 25% probability) was not the actual distribution.

Our answer: In the debriefing stage of the experiment, we clarified all these aspects to our participants. This experimental design is quite common when dealing with the hide behind the small effect under asymmetric information contexts. Our experimental design was approved by the Ethical Committee of our University with CAAE 10331719.0.0000.0020.

Reviewer 1: Table 1 needs the standard deviations and the means.

Our answer: Done!

Reviewer 1: What were the criteria for selecting participants?

Our answer: Our participants were young adult college students from a business school (majoring in economics, business administration, or accounting). When they arrived at the experiment, we used a list of criteria to allow them to participate, such as not having to eat or drink anything (besides water), use tobacco, brush their teeth, or engage in any exercise three hours before.

Reviewer 1: What are the standard deviations for the offers (Table 3)?

Our answer: The standard deviation in Table 3 measured how dispersed was the offers to the mean.

Reviewer 1: Could you elaborate on 'the costs of deceiving the responder'?

Our answer: When the participant sends an offer that conveys the idea that the "cake" is smaller than it is, we have the "hide behind the small cake effect. The cost of deceiving means the psychological cost of a lie, which leads people to not incur in the "hide behind the small cake effect" preferring to make less money to avoid lying. In the manuscript, we replaced the "costs of deceiving" with "the psychological costs of deceiving.

Reviewer 1: It would also be interesting to see a bar chart showing a distribution of offers by reported beliefs about the responder's guess in the two groups (a combination of Figures 2 and 3).

Our answer: We did some tests to show how it would be. It seems that it might be confusing to understand... Please, look at the figures below. (please see the attached file)

Quadrants A1 (without stress stimulus) and A2 (with stress stimulus) showed that without stress stimulus, proposers believed that the second player would be prone to infer that the actual amount was ten while A2, the beliefs regarding the second player's guess were nearer to the actual amount.

Reviewer 1: Regarding the regression models, it is interesting to see the relationships between stress and offers. However, your Belief variable is an interaction between stress treatment and the belief the responders guessed the true endowment correctly. While you do have Stress in Models 3 to 5, the main effect of the belief the responders thought the true endowment correctly is missing from all the models where Beliefs is used, and Stress is missing from Model 2. I suggest adding both the main effects and the interaction term.

Our answer: Models 3 to 5 in the first version (now models 4 to 6) were stimulated using both variables, stress, and beliefs. For this revision, we added a new regression using stress and beliefs in the same model as recommended. The results were incorporated into the paper.

Reviewer 1: For your cortisol variable, it would make sense to use cortisol levels at Time 2, rather than the difference between Time 1 and Time 2, as your independent variable. That would account for the actual stress rather than for the effectiveness of the stress treatment.

Our answer: The main reason for not using cortisol levels at time 2 was that people have different baseline cortisol levels. So each person has a specific cortisol level; maybe a higher level for one can be low for another. In any way, we reestimated model 2 using the time two cortisol collection, and the results were similar to model 2, so its insertion in the paper will not be necessary unless the reviewer sees this aspect as relevant. Please, look at the regression model below.

Reviewer 1: Finally, a rationale for using the Tobit regression is warranted. Do you expect the actual values to extend beyond the observed data? If so, why?

Our Answer: We adopted the Tobit model because we dealt with censored variables since the lower and Upper limits to offers in the game were between 0 and 30. We do not expect that true values would extend beyond the observed data, that is why we use estimated our tobit regressions using the syntax "Tobit y variable x variables, ll(0) ul(30), where the lower limit was specified in parentheses after ll, and the upper limit was set in parentheses after ul.

Reviewer 1: The claim that most of the literature on decision-making and stress shows that stressed individuals usually search for a reward that benefits them can be easily contested. How are your findings situated within the existing literature? E.g., there has been a lot of research on negative affect and risk perception, and on risk perception and risk-taking.

Our answer: Our findings suggested that stressed people are not constantly searching for a reward but can increase their risk perception when under stress. Our results corroborated some researchers dedicated to the study relation between stress and risk perception. Only to mention some of them, we have George Loewenstein, that explored how emotions, including stress, can influence risk perception and decision-making processes; Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky that conducted research on cognitive biases and heuristics that affect decision-making, including risk perception; Baruch Fischhoff conducted extensive research on how stress and emotions can impact individuals' risk perceptions; and Donald Broadbent, which study explored the effects of stress on attentional processes and how stress can affect perception and decision-making. Thus, our results are situated according to the supra-mentioned authors.

Reviewer 1: Do you expect the participants' majors (economics, business administration, or accounting) to influence how they approached the task? Economics majors may be familiar with the ultimatum game.

Our answer: Economic games are part of the behavioral economics discipline, which is part of a new curricular matrix for the economics course, reserved to take place only a few months after the experiment. Besides, this discipline belongs to the same professor that conducted this experiment. For this reason, we were sure this content had not been previously studied.

Reviewer 1: Since some participants (only in the stress condition) offered 0 or 30, both of which would result in them getting 0, is it likely that they misunderstood or forgot the instructions (potentially because of the stress)?

Our answer: After explaining the game's rules, we made some checking questions to ensure understanding. Besides, we encourage participants to raise their hands and ask questions about the game's rules. However, we can not assure that the stress might not have influenced the understanding of some participants. In any way, we believe this effect was small since we made all the efforts to ensure understanding.

Reviewer 2:

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Meg Kiseleva

Date review returned: August 24, 2023

Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

The authors have done a good job of the revision and I think the paper can be published once the typo on Line 57 is corrected; the word "a" is missing from the phrase "Hiding behind a small cake effect". In fact, I notice that the phrase is sometimes placed in quotations and sometimes not. I think it is best italicized without any quotations.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

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Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).: None

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 1. Excellent

Authors' Responses

Dear Editor,

Thank you for all your kind support during the submission process. We have made all the required changes and the new files can be recognized by the label R2 (Round 2), before the file's name. Thus, I inserted 3 documents: 1. manuscript with control changes; 2. manuscript without control changes and 3. the answers to the reviewers.

The research data was uploaded to Mendeley Platform, as required. The link is below.

<https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/wfhh9gxsm/1>

DOI: 10.17632/wfhh9gxsm.1

Any questions/doubts, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Best Wishes